

***WU, Z. (2020). "A Corpus-Based Study of Translation of Metaphor in The Economist's Coverage Related to China"* Vol:1, Issue: 4 pp: 510-516**

Keywords: metaphor, China's image, The Economist, corpus-based

Article Type

Research Article

A Corpus-Based Study of Translation of Metaphor in The Economist's Coverage Related to China

Arrived Date	Accepted Date	Published Date
10.10.2020	15.10.2020	31.10.2020

Zheng Wu *

ABSTRACT

As China's comprehensive economy continues to grow, the attention of the world also has been drawn to various incidents in our country. Therefore, foreign media are also increasingly targeting China and reporting on China more and more. *The Economist* from January 28th, 2012 issue has opened up a special column to report on China, and to provide more layout for China. As an important figure of speech, the wide use of metaphor makes the news report vivid and accessible. However, the application of metaphor also embodies the author's personal attitude and emotions. The consequence of this poses the challenges for news translation. The translation of the metaphor cannot only understand the literal meaning of the words or phrases, but also should extend their connotations. In this paper, several reports related to China in *The Economists* have been selected as case study, and analyzes the translation of the metaphor. By combining with software such as Antconc, study the usage of certain words explores the processing method in translating metaphor by case analysis based on corpus. Through the study of its coverage can understand how foreign media present the contemporary China image in *The Economist*.

INTRODUCTION

Metaphors are found everywhere in all kinds of news and periodicals. They increase the readability and vividness of news and periodicals. The text in newspapers and periodicals is the bridge of communication between the author and the reader. If you want to understand the contents of author's writing accurately, it is the key to understand the author's purpose of writing. Appropriate understanding of metaphors in foreign media news is an important step in translating texts. The metaphors used in the news media are not limited to the superficial meaning of the metaphor, but also need to be translated into different contexts meanings after being understood by some background knowledge and connotations. As China's comprehensive national power continues to grow and its role in the international community is increasingly important, the foreign media have shifted their attention to more coverage of China. The focus of this study lies in *The Economist*. This magazine is leading in all areas of its reporting and has been able to make numerous comments sharply on the realities as it has a huge influence on the mass media and the public. In the past decade, *The Economist* has continuously increased the volume reporting about China. Through the study of its coverage can understand how foreign media set the issue of China and present the contemporary China image in a newspaper article. Many linguists in China are keen to introduce and study Western metaphor theories in recent years, but most of them neglect to use them for the translation. The corpus selects the English-Chinese parallel corpus composed of *The Economists* reports on China and extracts the material using software such as Antconc. In addition, Using BNC (British National Corpus) to study the usage of certain words, and then analyze them one by one. The theme of this paper attempts to through the coverage of China by *The Economist* and the cultural differences between Western and China as well as the reporters' political tendency and personal emotion.

* City University of Hong Kong, /CHINA, zhengwu6-c@my.cityu.edu.hk

LITERATURE

National image represents group expression and affiliation of the whole nation. The image is characterized by habits and conventions, including the used language, the implemented practice, the dressed clothing and so on. The conceptual metaphor embody daily practice, while image is presented, particularly when conceptual metaphor used, through these trivial things of life to present different image categories. From the individual perspective, image features in personal unique and distinctiveness. As such, the conceptual metaphor among diverse industries show the image a person involved in society. As discussed in the work (Banwart, 2006), the female politicians employ metaphors in their political speeches to respond the image of pioneer, puppet, hostess/beauty queen, and unruly woman. For instance, metaphors of personal figure, "TRAILBLAZER or GROUNDBREAKER", and of characteristics "determination, practical wisdom, perseverance", to reach out "PIONEER" image. For an English instructor, a work (Zhu & Zhu, 2018) shows the professional image transfers after the teaching practicums. Raised by this, Chinese teachers' image metaphors are art-oriented, and twisted with animal-related metaphors including frog, parrot, deer, and eagle. By contrast, the American participants stick to subject-oriented and progressive metaphors, like cells, coach, and captain, to elucidate their professional roles. Indeed, the GOAL-AS-JOURNEY metaphors, as a form of motivation, imply academic possible identities (Landau, Oyserman, Keefer, & Smith, 2014). Moving from the individual to the group section, metaphor also can be readily used in different organizations to build distinctive enterprise culture and create the strong atmosphere, like "DEMOCRACY" metaphor to school image (Brandt, 2004) and entrepreneurship metaphor in business management (Chmielecki, 2017).

When the definition of group is becoming general, the image of political party and religious group are under discussion. This book introduces BUILD, JOURNEY CUSTOM and GLOBALISATION IS AN INDEPENDENT ENTITY in the target domain of the mapping process to reflect the changing new Labor's image. For instance, the analysis of POLITICS IS A JOURNEY relies on a custom-made semantic concept that includes the journey-related words, as well as the lemma MOVE. Meanwhile, with the transformation of the Russian politics, the leading party is displaced, shifting the principle from dictatorship to democracy. As a result, AUTHORITARIAN metaphors decline even more sharply and are replaced by metaphors of CHOICE (Anderson, 2001). In terms of religion, the image, exactly the ethnical image, of followers is defined by ritual-like manner metaphors. According to the Christian, the Bible as an Ethical History, and God is the source of love and fair. Also, the image of the Psalmist is associated with the "FOREIGN" and "HELPLESS" metaphors in the Old Testament (Southwood, 2018). However, the attitude of foreign media towards China can revoke the issue of national image development. It is worth questioning what forms of image underlying metaphor words in the media coverage. Moreover, the adequate number of coverages need to be used as research material, which is also the form of corpus, because the diachronic corpus is more appropriately empirical data onto the national image shaping processing.

METHODS

Definition of Metaphor

"We have found, on the contrary, that metaphor is pervasive in everyday life, not just in language but in thought and action. Our ordinary conceptual system, in terms of which we both think and act, is fundamentally metaphorical in nature." (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Conceptual metaphor is the manifestation of linguistic metaphor, and the conventional expression in human language is essentially the metaphor of the past. Metaphor have evolved into the common expressions of the people today through thousands of years of their predecessors' long-term usage. Metaphor is a deep structure in our thinking that covers many aspects of the individual such as nation, culture, environment, values, etc. The ability of understanding and using metaphor is not at the same level for everyone, rather connecting the experience of the speaker and his imagination.

Introduction to Antconc

Antconc is a freeware corpus analysis toolkit for concordance and text analysis. There are seven main areas including Concordance, Concordance Plot, File View, Clusters, Word list, and Keyword list. Concordance tool is mainly used in this paper. In keywords part, there are some typical keywords to be discussed. Then through knowing the features of their surroundings is a useful way to dig up the features of these typical words. Antconc can generate KWIC concordance lines. Concordance tool in Antconc is used in this paper.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on BNC corpus, this paper through the study of its coverage to understand how foreign media set the issue of China and present the contemporary China image in *The Economist*. The research questions are:

- 1) What the author's attitude in using the metaphor to write the China's coverage?
- 2) What the translation strategies of metaphor adopted by the translators to present the China's image?
- 3) The thesis makes a presentation of how *The Economist* shaping China's images by answering the above-mentioned questions and analyzing the metaphor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Literal Translation of the Cultural Vehicle and the Explanation of the Connotation

In the process of translating the metaphor in the original passage, the cultural features in the original English texts cannot be reflected in Chinese one due to differences in cultural connotation and social background. However, in order to ensure the authenticity of the original text, firstly we adopted the literal translation method and maintained the metaphorical features. If literal translation fails to "be consistent with" different cultural vehicles in Chinese, we can make up for the lack of cultural vehicle according to the context and adopt the strategy of "explanation" translation of cultural vehicle.

E.g.1

Original : China is often dubbed a Lehman-in-the-making.

Translation : 中國經常被稱作“一個正在形成的雷曼兄弟”。

Lehman here is a metaphor. Literal translation of Lehman may puzzle readers who do not know its historical background. At this point translation should be combined with background knowledge, adding annotation: "the fourth largest investment bank in the United States, Lehman (Brothers) in the sub-prime mortgage market crisis through the intensified situation, eventually throwing a hatchet, announced the application for bankruptcy protection." Lehman is the largest subscriber to sub-prime mortgage securities in 2006, accounting for 11% market share. In 2007, many Wall Street firms suffered losses due to improper investment in sub-prime mortgage loans, and Lehman still made a profit of 4.1 billion U.S. dollars. The author uses the phrase "Lehman" as a metaphor for "there is uncertainty about the true size of its debts and how much of them will be repaid." The implication of Lehman's tragedy suggests that China should recognize the current debt situation and should not just care about the immediate benefits. The addition of annotation here guarantees the principle of making up for the lack of cultural figurative language according to the context, preserves the cultural vehicle of the English metaphor and its meaning showing in the translated text.

E.g.2

Original: Paper tiger, roaring dragon.

Translation: 紙老虎 · 咆哮龍。

E.g.3

Original: By contrast, the private sector is full of young dragons exposed to the Schumpeterian forces of creative destruction.

Translation: 相比之下，在私營部門裡有眾多年輕的“猛龍”飽經熊彼特式創造性顛覆的洗禮。

Paper tiger, roaring dragon is a common saying of our Chinese. Paper tiger refers to buckram, roaring dragon means strong and powerful force. Paper Tiger in these passage metaphors for China's state-owned business, roaring Dragon metaphors for the private business, using our familiar figure. During translating, if the target reader is Chinese, literal translation can be satisfied. Because this method not only preserves the cultural image of the metaphor also makes the reader cognate the metaphorical characteristics and the cultural meanings in the original textual. Metaphor comes from thinking, deciding implication. Therefore, there has no metaphor without thinking, and without thinking, there is no correct understanding of metaphor. It is the private sector, not state capitalism, which is responsible for modern China's economic rise. Sentences in the following confirm the deeper meaning of the previous metaphor. In my opinion, state capitalism translates to “國家資本主義” is not proper, for its context, it better to be translated to “中國公有制經濟”.

E.g.4

Original: ...the IMF decided to include the Yuan in the basket from next year, joining the dollar, the euro, the pound and the yen.

Translation: IMF決定從明年起接納人民幣“入籃”，“籃子”裡已有的貨幣包括美元、歐元、英鎊和日元。

If the literal translation of the word “bracket” is a bit similar to jargon, the reader may understand that the RMB has new measures in the currency circulation, but most readers are unable to understand exactly what the measure refers to. “bracket” is a metaphor at this time, rather than literal basket. However, as a container, figurative image has no direct correspondence. Adding note that the IMF formally approved the RMB as a reserve currency - making it a safe, liquid asset that governments can put their minds. By adding comments to familiarize readers with the specifics of stories, it helps to understand the following description of this action. Such information is added to make the translation more specific and credible.

The above example illustrates that in the process of dealing with metaphorical translation of social and cultural backgrounds in China in *The Economist*, after the pursuit of completion of translation, the image of the metaphor in Chinese thinking can be “mapped” to the reader of English translation. Firstly taking literal translation method. Because when the author wrote the news, he took into account that most of the readers are Chinese, the metaphors adopted in the passage also that Chinese more familiar to. Direct translation can convey the direct meaning of the author, and the reader understands the meanings behind the metaphor. For most articles after reading the whole of it, we can know the meaning of the preceding metaphor. When taking literal translation, the reader looks at the reported event from his own cognitive perspective, ensuring that, as the translator does not add his or her own feelings during translation. However, some of the metaphors from the social events of foreign media countries, using literal translation not making readers understand well the meaning behind the translation, at this time translation should be combined with the current social background and historical knowledge to verify the reference to the vehicle. Searching for the metaphorical shift of meaning that is used in other contexts is another way. Due to the different cultural backgrounds between China and the West, the selection of vehicles are different (Semino, Demjén, & Demmen, 2018). At this time, we should combine the deep meaning of the metaphor in the country where we live, and translate it with connotation. In the process of bilingual translation, it can be said that “both languages are comparatively analyzed from time to time, so as to speak: no comparison, there is no translation.” (Markman & Markman, 1989) Methods combing them, it is best to convey the author's true intentions in keeping with the principles of his cultural image.

Conversion Translation and Weakening Methods of Critical Awareness

Owing to the objective differences in political stand among different countries, the creating and release of many news reports are deeply influenced by their national ideology. Correspondingly, translation process is no longer just the conversion of two languages at the literal level, but taking into account many factors that outside or beyond the language, such as the impact of political background the

original impact, need to change at the language level at the same time. Therefore, it is necessary for us to use the method of critical discourse analysis, using the BNC corpus to know certain words bringing subjective attitude used to depict China. Studying on expressions on the media report to find out the hidden ideology and the metaphor of personal emotion when translating foreign media reports on China.

E.g.5

Original: Since 2008 credit growth in the Middle Kingdom, has exploded, and by some estimates is over 200% of GDP.

Translation: 自2008年起中國信貸開始增長，已經爆炸，並且據估計，其債務已經相當於GDP的200%左右。

E.g.6

Original: but the inexorable accumulation of debt would sap the economy's vigor and raise the specter of a fearsome crash.

Translation: 但債務積累的不斷加重將削弱經濟活力，中國將面臨金融體系崩潰的可怕厄運。

According to the BNC corpus, the most frequent collocation of the word “explode” is the explode bomb, followed by threatens, violence, etc. The word “crash” means an accident, its connotation means devastating result. Instead, those two used in reports of China's economic markets presented an image of a worse and gloomy outlook. “Foreign scholars researching forecast about economic generally applying multiple deductive methods,” (Moran, 1989) to make a hypothetical study, that is, put forward several hypotheses before the argument, and then prove whether falsify one by one during demonstration process. Conclusions getting from this deductive analysis are often very specific, targeted, diversified, but relatively this kind of research lack the feature of summary. Namely, conclusions apply only to specific events or a specific period of time, the lack of adaptability in research conclusions, research theories and methods at home. Without mentioning the both side of the accuracy “the same quarterly and last quarterly figures published in China” in the text that follows, the author directly chose negative words. From this aspect, the author is skeptical about the prospects of market economy in China. In the process of translation should show prominent emotion of astonishment, not the panic of the data. This expression can be translated into “令人擔憂是中國很有可能將面臨金融體系崩潰的可怕厄運”. Weaken the strong verbs, blur and neutralize the words with negative meanings.

E.g.7

Original: Finance in China the subtitle- big but brittle

Translation: “大”卻“脆弱”的中國經濟。

(Proportion of “brittle” used in the news to that in the BNC context 23/442)

The word “big”, “brittle” are generally to describe the external characteristic and nature of the objective. According to the BNC corpus, the word “brittle” is collocated with “hard”, “fracture”, “dry”, etc. The explanation of the word “brittle” in the Oxford Advanced Learner's English-Chinese Dictionary is having little elasticity; hence easily cracked or fractured or snapped. Although indeed a slowdown in the economy at the time, it also was mentioned in other newspapers, liquidity buffers are strong. The usage of words here is exaggerated, despite of a large number of theoretical data in this article covering the Chinese economy. However, the report has unceasingly questioned the fact that China, as an economic power, has been flooded with fictitious figures. Therefore, out of his own doubtful attitude, the author exaggerates the fact in some places by using big words. Because of that, readers feel that the Chinese market is facing a bleak prospect; however, the reality is China's economy has slowed down recently. In order to make RMB more international, China opened up its bond banks to overseas institutional investors, the success outweighing the risks of economic. The author selectively reported and focused his efforts on the area of economic problems but did not report it in the light of the measures that the departments concerned responded to. Double quotation marks are added here

to make the original words having special meanings, thereby weakening the original meaning of the exaggerated words to make readers think of deep implications behind this crisis.

E.g.8

Original: Chinese expansive prompts a clash of arms in the South China Sea.

Translation: 中國挑起南海軍事衝突。

(Proportion of “prompt” used in the news to that in the BNC context 1/763)

E.g.9

Original: ...the ship and crew were released only after intense economic and political pressure from China.

Translation: 直到中國施加巨大的經濟、政治壓力後，該船和工作人員才得以被釋放。

The first one above extracted from the Economist Intelligence Unit has released in March this year, the world's top ten of the most crisis things in current have a far-reaching impact. One thing in these involved China, the author uses verb “prompt” for military issues in the South China Sea. According to BNC corpus, the most frequency of this word's collocation is prompt action, and the voice in the context is positive. The explanation of the word “prompt” in the Oxford Advanced Learner's English-Chinese Dictionary is that prompt someone to do something means to make him or her decide to do it. Thus, using it implied this behavior proactively aroused by China and China is the party that provoked the dispute over the South China Sea. As we knew, all of those contradict the fact! Metaphors rightly applies to depict the issue of the South China Sea. The perspective of foreign media contains strong emotional dissatisfaction towards China's action to the issue of the South China Sea. The second one is also related to the coverage about the issue of South China Sea. From it we can further see the Western media's personal preference towards the South China Sea issue. Combing with the background, a Chinese fishing vessel had been detained by a Japanese oil tanker in the waters near the dispute island, and the Japanese government used this to provoke a dispute. In the original article, China is intended to exert pressure by adopting coercive measures that make China's original legitimacy and safeguarding seem like the state's sovereignty. The translation can revised as “中國通過經濟、政治上的交涉後，該船和工作人員得以被釋放。”

CONCLUSIONS

As a public, we knew the current world affairs and cognate states mostly through the media. *The Economist*, an authoritative magazine, has influenced readers both at home and abroad. Using the metaphor cleverly in its reports, the authors integrate their own emotions and comments into the texts, thus giving readers different psychological feelings. Due to reports from foreign media, the shaping of the “image of China” is inevitably subject to ideological prejudice in terms of its content, themes, tendencies and the construction of sentences. In the process of translating metaphors, different cultural, social conditions and other factors should be taken into account. Firstly, we should have a certain sensitivity to the metaphor, find the metaphor and combine the background knowledge to understand the metaphorical meaning and understand the ideology behind the metaphorical position. The BNC corpus can be used to find the certain words' collection and find out the most frequency of them as well as considering the contexts using this collocation. It is necessary to faithfully express the information and content conveyed by the original text in the process of translation, but not to interpret the meaning of original text words by words. The literal and explanation translation of the cultural figurative form with the original text. When encountering a word with strong personal emotion, after making a critical analysis, revealing the implicit meanings behind the textual discourse, making the appropriate addition and deletion or adjustments, blurring the author's personal affective tendencies, neutralizing the translation or conversing translation, weakening the ideology in original text in line with the purpose of the reader's values and reading expectations. At the same time, we should fully consider the impact that the translation has on the targeted readers so that readers in our countries can understand the outside world's views and opinions on current affairs in China.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, R. D. (2001). Metaphors of dictatorship and democracy: Change in the Russian political lexicon and the transformation of Russian politics. *Slavic Review*, 60(2), 312-335.
- Banwart, M. C. (2006). Governing Codes: Gender, Metaphor, and Political Image. *Politics & Gender*, 2(4), 534-536.
- Brandt, N. C. (2004). Constructing school organization through metaphor: Making sense of school reform. The Florida State University,
- Chmielecki, M. (2017). *Metaphors in management : blend of theory and practice*. Frankfurt am Main New York, NY: PL Academic Research.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphor we live by*. Chicago/London.
- Landau, M. J., Oyserman, D., Keefer, L. A., & Smith, G. C. (2014). The college journey and academic engagement: How metaphor use enhances image-based motivation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 106(5), 679.
- Markman, P. T., & Markman, R. H. (1989). *Masks of the spirit: image and metaphor in Mesoamerica*: Univ of California Press.
- Moran, R. (1989). Seeing and believing: Metaphor, image, and force. *Critical inquiry*, 16(1), 87-112.
- Semino, E., Demjén, Z., & Demmen, J. (2018). An integrated approach to metaphor and framing in cognition, discourse, and practice, with an application to metaphors for cancer. *Applied linguistics*, 39(5), 625-645.
- Southwood, K. (2018). Metaphor, illness, and image in Psalms 88 and 102. *Journal for the Study of the Old Testament*, 43(2), 228-246.
- Zhu, J., & Zhu, G. (2018). Understanding student teachers' professional image transformation through metaphor: An international perspective. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 44(4), 500-504.